
COMMUNICATION WITH RADIO JOURNALISM AS ONE OF THE CHARACTERISTICS OF A JOURNALIST

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844300>

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Annotation.

the article of the radio audience and the university exam, education matters, is a true sign of yurutilgan's thought.

Taser.

radio audience, radio channel, trucker, Sur, interview, huzhatlar analysis.

The connection of radio with the audience begins from the first moments of broadcasting. One of the common manifestations of communication is the direct invitation of listeners to various manifestations of superficial cooperation. It seems to us that it is through cooperation that the journalist's relationship with the audience works well. Because in this, the journalist, without noticing the listener, is seriously working on increasing his worldview and level of knowledge. The method of invitation to cooperation will help both journalists and listeners to unite into one pan-media. This plays a significant psychological role for the audience.

The fact that broadcasts and messages are received by hearing, and the listener can be distracted from the broadcast for various reasons, therefore, at the same time as effective communication with the audience, it is necessary to keep in touch with the listener throughout the broadcast, journalists should not forget for a minute.

According to experts in the field of broadcasting theory and practice, the simpler and more typical the broadcast is for listeners, the less formal character and solemn sound will be in it. Such information is perceived more closely and intelligibly, more firmly remembered, that is, its effectiveness is ensured. This is the most fundamental function of radio journalism.

Many of the broadcast heroes are not used to speaking in front of the microphone and are often mistaken at the time of recording, lose themselves, etc. Journalists prepare them for writing for a long time. They write a written text and repeatedly copy it back to the magnetic tape. It is considered one of the difficulties encountered in the Daily, simple activities of radio journalists. But in some cases,

among the heroes of the broadcast, there are also those who do not behave less than qualified radio journalists in front of the microphone. Such heroes will be able to easily connect communication with the audience, even if they will be able to cope with this task better. But often examples of this are also encountered. Such cases arise at times when the broadcast effect drops dramatically, as a result of journalists not attaching sufficient importance to the rules of broadcast operation and its specific aspects. This is also the case when journalists become obsessed with reading material texts and broadcast long messages without stopping or adjusting their breath. In doing so, the audience gets tired quickly, and it stops receiving information, as a result of which mutual communication is interrupted.

Skillful communication with the audience is one of the important, distinctive features of radio journalism. Since such communication has distinct features that are invisible, surface-to-surface, unique only in that their skillful use helps radio journalists make more complete use of the dominant aspects of radio from a media perspective.

It is very important for a radio journalist to study the audience: what impression the message made on the listener, what was the effect of the system of broadcasts in general-these are decisive in determining the effectiveness of broadcasts.

The development of SMSs in later times is also becoming more important in the study of different audiences. Listeners report their feedback on their listening broadcasts via SMS. assessments of feedback, broadcasts are studied through SMS and come to certain conclusions. Before studying radio auditoria, it is necessary to find out its purpose and essence.

The basic principles of audience learning are divided into two: the study of the influence of the audience on the media; answers to a number of questions are obtained.

Questionnaire surveys-knowledge of thoughts, assessment, knowledge of relationships, study. At the same time, it is possible to know how many subscribers to newspapers, magazines, broadcasters. And through interviews, it is also possible to conduct questionnaire surveys. The purpose of the questionnaire: to illuminate the original purpose of the survey. After starting the questionnaire with simple questions, it is necessary to go to complex questions. Questions should be growing. Those who do not hear the radio, on the other hand, refuse to answer on their own, difficult questions should be in the middle of the questionnaire. The questionnaire should include closed, Open, semi-open questions. These are: closed question: this

means choosing one answer. Open question: this is a question that can be answered freely. For example, would you like to listen to broadcasts with which or whose participation? Semi-openwork: this is also closer to the latter, but it is imperative that a specific professional is indicated in it.

Radio auditoria is also studied through Special Studies: survey, document analysis, observation methods, article, book, dissertations, etc. K.

Surveys are a method used to identify thoughts, attitudes, assessments, purpose-reasons (motivations) related to the respondent's personal (subjective) world. Also, a number of objective-style facts are determined: the presence of radio prim's, subscriptions to newspapers, listening to facts, etc.

There are questionnaire and interview types of surveys. Like any study, the questionnaire survey provides for the exact setting of the problem, the choice of the subject and object of the study, the identification of its goals and objectives, the development of measurement methods, programs. The survey objectives must be clear and appropriate and scientifically secured. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the social layer of the audience.

The questionnaire usually starts at the entrance. The purpose of the introduction is to convince the respondent to appreciate the importance of cooperation in the survey, to fill out anonymity requirements, to return the schedule questionnaire. The questionnaire asks first simple, unbiased (neutral), then perfect questions.

An interview is a type of request based on the personal interview of the interviewer with the respondent. Many of the requirements of the questionnaire also apply to the interview. In an interview, the opportunity to deeply enter the world of the individual is used.

Document analysis. Spiritual analysis (content analysis) is widely used in the study of radio auditoria. This process is mainly used when analyzing the content of mail and broadcasts.

One of the important tasks of the analysis of radio broadcasts is the separation of radio content and accounting units of an adequate nature, the consideration of not only written texts, but also information that is being scanned. The reason is, the listener receives radio broadcasts by ear, and his attitude to the information being broadcast is developed. Written texts are naturally much drier than sound, because folders often do not have all the analysis of reportage records, interviews, etc. Therefore, the researcher must hear the broadcasts he is analyzing several times in

advance. Especially this requirement will be needed when writing a review of works of radio journalism.

Observation is a method based on the advancement of facts and events directly by their witnesses. Observation must be developed according to a pre-scientific program. In it, mainly isolated objects, their known descriptions and manifestations of qualities were observed. There are direct and indirect manifestations of observations. In indirect observation, The Observer is selected from representatives of a particular group to inform the researchers (e.g., about the reception of radio broadcasts in their environment). And in indirect observation, the audience is studied from the outside. Observations are divided into "field" (conducted under natural conditions) and laboratory observations, depending on the state in which they are conducted. The first method was used when there were convenient opportunities to observe radio broadcasting, that is, when listening to broadcasts in public squares, Culture houses, clubs. Now the radio is mainly listened to in a narrow circle or personal (individual), and laboratory observations are the most optimal method for studying radio auditoria. Most often, the observation method is used in combination with other methods.

With the above methods, an attempt is made to know the desires, requirements, interests of the audience, as well as the effectiveness of broadcasts, shortcomings or achievements. This is among the main factors in improving the quality of broadcasts.

Nowadays, the relationship between journalists and audiences has changed a lot. Not every listener will leave their comments about this on "Facebook" or "Twitter" after listening to informational programs. Not everyone contributes to the preparation of informational applications using their smart phone or other mobile devices, receiving text information. Some can read news over the internet, but do not want to comment in response. But the members of the audience in the big are doing a lot of work that caused the development of the novelty program to change. The one-way information flow is now moving in two ways: from the information transmitter to the audience and from the audience to the information distributor. Some analysts assess this as communication between journalists and audiences. Such a conversation can give a positive result. Journalists can witness their preferences expressed by their audience on Facebook. On the one hand, when mistakes are clearly visible, in social forums the audience will have the opportunity to express their opinion about this. Now journalists are faced with unprecedented control of an audience with their own voice and a high level of knowledge.

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